

Artificial Intelligence in Second Language Writing

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ABSTRACT

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly integrated into educational contexts, but its impact on students' writing processes remains under explored, particularly in second language (L2) settings. Understanding how students perceived and utilized AI tools can provide insights into their writing practices and challenges. This study investigated the extent of L2 students' reliance on AI tools in writing and examined the tools' impact on their writing skills. A mixed-method approach was employed. Quantitative data were collected from 437 students enrolled in English courses during the A222 semester, while qualitative insights were gathered through interviews with five selected students. The findings indicated that students occasionally rely on AI tools, particularly to enhance vocabulary, efficiency, and assignment quality. Most students expressed positive attitudes toward the use of AI tools, emphasizing their role in facilitating better writing outcomes. However, over-reliance on AI was found to hinder the development of critical thinking and independent writing skills. While AI tools offer significant advantages in supporting L2 students' writing, educators should provide guidance to balance their usage. This ensured that students benefit from AI tools without compromising essential writing and cognitive skill development.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence; Second Language Writing; Writing Process; Reliance Level.

INTRODUCTION

Background on Student Writing in Malaysia, L2 Learners

English writing in Malaysia has a rich and diverse background. English is considered the second language in Malaysia (BM) and is officially used by the Association of South-East Nations (ASEAN) and the United Nations; where it serves as a global lingua franca for both native and non-native speakers in daily conversations (Siddek & Ismail, 2021). Teaching and learning in Malaysia, particularly in higher education, are conducted primarily in English. Most student assignments and evaluations are carried out in English. Students must therefore know how to write effectively in English. However, due to the interference of students' first language, Bahasa Malaysia, these students may find writing as difficult (Mehat & Ismail, 2021).

The Change in Education due to Technology (AI)

The utilisation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has gained immense popularity in education, specifically in academic writing. Given its fundamental role in higher education and research, the acquisition of academic writing skills is crucial for students to master (Dong, 2023). As a result, this rise in AI technology has provided language learners with increased opportunities to enhance their language acquisition and writing skills. Nevertheless, there is a mounting apprehension about the effect of AI on students' writing proficiency, particularly for second language (L2) learners. This

study aims to investigate the reliance level of L2 students on AI in developing their ideas and writing, as well as the impact of AI on L2 students' development of ideas and writing.

As the emergence of AI has sparked a transformative shift in education, it is imperative for Malaysia to integrate AI into its education system. This involves incorporating AI into the curriculum, enabling student engagement in creating AI systems and applications (Hamzah, 2024). The integration of AI in education also benefits educators and instantly reduces their workload, such as through computerised grading, personalised learning based on students' performance, homework preparation, and task management (Owoc et al., 2019). Dong (2023) also highlighted that educators may optimise the teaching of academic English writing by improving their instructional approaches, offering students more effective and prompt feedback, and enhancing their skills when incorporating AI into their teaching methods.

LITERATURE REVIEW

AI in Second Language Writing

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) technologies in second language (L2) writing education has garnered significant attention in recent years. Tools such as ChatGPT and Wordtune exemplify the growing application of AI in facilitating writing development. Zhao (2023) highlighted that Wordtune assists English as a Foreign Language (EFL) writers by offering rephrasing options, improving coherence, and providing suggestions tailored to various tones and lengths. This not only aids writers in overcoming language barriers but also supports their cognitive engagement in the writing process through self-directed learning.

Similarly, Barrot (2023) emphasized ChatGPT's role as a tutor for L2 learners, providing immediate feedback on grammar, syntax, and vocabulary. Its capability to generate contextually relevant text aids learners in organizing ideas and improving overall writing coherence. ChatGPT also serves as an effective platform for practice, allowing learners to experiment with language use in a low-pressure environment, which is critical for building confidence in L2 writing.

AI tools also play a pivotal role in addressing traditional challenges in L2 writing pedagogy. As Tseng and Warschauer (2023) argued, incorporating AI-based tools like ChatGPT into the classroom can help educators move beyond conventional teaching methods by fostering digital literacy alongside language skills. They proposed a pedagogical framework that includes understanding, accessing, and ethically incorporating AI in writing instruction, ensuring that learners are equipped to navigate the evolving technological landscape.

However, despite their potential, concerns about the implications of these tools on academic integrity and writing pedagogy persist. Barrot (2023) pointed out that over-reliance on AI might impede the development of critical thinking and originality in writing. Furthermore, there is a need to develop guidelines for the ethical use of AI-generated content, particularly concerning plagiarism and proper attribution.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Research Design

This study employed a mixed-methods approach, incorporating both quantitative and qualitative data collection methods. The objective of this study is to examine the perspectives and opinions of students regarding AI applications in their writing.

Research Sample

The study was conducted at Universiti Utara Malaysia, a public university in Malaysia. The study utilised a probability sampling strategy to choose the sample. 437 (N) students participated in answering a set of questionnaires. The participants included were 318 (72%) female and 119 (27.2%) male.

Research Instrument

The data for this study was gathered using two main research instruments: questionnaires and interviews. The questionnaire was created via Google Forms. The survey comprised closed-ended questions using Likert scale options to evaluate participants' dependence on AI applications and the impact of AI on their writing. The items of the questionnaire were designed using previous studies as a basis. The adaptation was derived from the works of Ali et al. (2023), Li (2023), and Chan and Hu (2023).

Five students were interviewed extensively to understand the qualitative aspects of reliance on artificial intelligence and its impacts. By integrating these two measures, the study successfully captured the comprehensive scope of AI utilisation through the questionnaire and the profound insights of individual experiences through the interviews.

Analysis of Data

The quantitative data of the study was analysed using SPSS statistic version 29. The analysis process began with the researchers leveraging the descriptive statistics capabilities of SPSS to calculate a range of summary measures, such as the mean, median, and standard deviation, which provided a high-level overview of the data and served as a foundation for further exploration (Greatorex, 2015).

Following the collection of qualitative data through semi-structured interviews, the transcribing process commenced. The process entailed transcribing the video recordings into a textual transcript that faithfully captures the exact words and subtleties of the original exchanges.⁽¹³⁾ The transcripts obtained are highly valuable as they offer thorough and easily accessible documentation of the gathered information, serving as the main data source for the research analysis (McMullin, 2023).

FINDINGS AND ANALYSIS

Frequent Usage

Table 1 below shows the frequency usage of the participants in using the AI writing tools mentioned. In this section, the participants had to choose from the range of never, rarely, sometimes, often, always. The result shows that the participants rated sometimes with the mean score of 3.36, 3.06, and 3.34 for Quillbot, Grammarly, and ChatGPT respectively. However, a large number of participants rarely use Bard, with the mean score of 1.76 and standard deviation of 1.026.

Table 1. Frequent usage of AI writing tools.

Items	N	Mean	Std.Deviation
Quillbot	437	3.36	1.181
Grammarly	437	3.06	1.322
Bard	437	1.76	1.026
ChatGPT	437	3.34	1.187
Valid N (listwise)	437		

Source: Own elaboration.

The findings above can be supported by qualitative data from the study. The results reveal that the students often consult with AI tools such as Quillbot, Grammarly, Bard AI, and ChatGPT, particularly in their academic assignments, with most students reporting regular to high reliance.

Students A, C, and D show that they frequently use AI tools, while students B and E mentioned that they use the tools regularly.

“Every single time, very often, because it makes my job easier” (Student A).

“I would use it on my assignments, and I would say um, I would say like, regularly” (Student E).

Writing Process

Table 2 presents the findings of participants' perceptions of AI tools in assisting their writing. The participants' mean score for the statement 'write efficiently when they use AI writing tools' is 3.80. It shows that the students generally agree with the statement. They also agreed that when they use AI tools, they make their studies easier. The mean score is 3.87, with a standard deviation of 0.883. In addition, the mean score of the statement “Studying with AI writing tools can improve my writing skills” is 3.86, indicating it is leaned towards agree. Besides that, the students agree that AI writing tools are an effective way for the students to finish their written assignments. The mean score is 3.65, with the standard deviation of 0.939.

Table 2. Writing Process.

Items	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
I write efficiently when I use AI writing tools.	437	3.80	0.897
My study seems easier when I use AI writing tools.	437	3.87	0.883
Studying with AI writing tools can improve my writing skills.	437	3.86	0.899
AI writing tools are an effective way for me to finish my written assignments.	437	3.65	0.939
Valid N (listwise)	437		

Source: Own elaboration.

The qualitative findings also suggest that AI tools have positively influenced students' writing process in various ways. Student A reveals that AI tools such as ChatGPT have enhanced their sentences in more sophisticated vocabulary, making their writing sound more professional. Besides that, Student B finds AI tools helpful for maintaining a smooth writing flow, particularly when connecting ideas in essays. Another student also highlighted the use of Grammarly has improved them in reducing grammar mistakes, allowing for self-correction without needing a teacher's input.

"Before this, there's a lot of grammar mistakes. Now, in words, we can add a Grammarly shortcut, it will detect grammar mistakes). This has helped in my writing. Previously, we had to see teachers, to check, now we can just use AI to learn on our own" (Student C).

Regarding the speed of the students' writing process, the findings reveal that AI tools have improved that area a lot. When asked, students A and B both agreed that AI allows them to complete their assignments faster, especially when they are pressed with time and need to manage multiple tasks.

"Yes, without AI, I took a longer time to finish my assignments. With the existence of AI, I can complete my assignments faster" (Student A).

"Yes, especially when I have a lot of things on my plate. It helps me to have a shorter time to complete my writing. If I need to go debate, and at the same time, I must submit assignments, then I would use Bard to help me" (Student B).

Additionally, AI tools have influenced positively students' writing styles. The most prominent improved writing styles are in sentence structure, vocabulary, and formality.

"...I would say, the structure of the sentences is better, much better compared to the ones I did in semesters one and two" (Student A).

"Yes. For example, in formal correspondence, I believe that having this AI can make it more formal. It's very helpful in writing styles" (Student B).

"Yes. Because, when I write before, I will use normal and basic sentences. But after using AI, it helps to use bombastic words. It helps in using complicated vocab, and it provides suitable words" (Student C).

"My grammar and vocabulary because they can produce perfect sentences for me" (Student D).

Attitude

Table 3 depicts findings of participants' attitude towards AI tools in writing. It is reported that the students become more interested in writing when they use AI writing tools. The data shows the students are leaning towards agree, with the mean score of 3.59. In addition, they feel that they could improve their written assignments by using the tools, mean 3.87 and standard deviation 0.859.

Moreover, the participants gave an average rating of 3.68, indicating that they generally like and feel good about using AI writing tools for their studies. Subsequently, the participants agree that they feel confident in their writing when they use AI writing tools, with the mean score of 3.65 and standard deviation 0.933. However, the participants scored they agree that they are over reliant to the AI tools, mean 3.37 and standard deviation of 1.032. They also disagreed with paying for premium access to the AI writing tools, a mean score of 2.59.

Table 3. Attitude.

Items	N	Mean	Std. Deviation
I become more interested in writing when I use AI writing tools.	437	3.59	0.984
I wish I could improve my written assignments by using AI writing tools.	437	3.87	0.859
I like using AI writing tools for my study.	437	3.68	0.941
I feel good about using AI writing tools.	437	3.68	0.941
I feel confident in my writing when I use AI writing tools.	437	3.65	0.933
I am willing to pay the fees for premium access to AI writing tools.	437	2.59	1.242
I am over reliant when I use AI writing tools.	437	3.37	1.032
Valid N (listwise)	437		

Source: Own elaboration.

The qualitative findings reveal that the students believe that they can write without the assistance of AI tools but are more confident with it, particularly when they are required to write in English language.

“I don't think I can write better, in the context of English. Because I feel like English has so many approaches, sometimes we don't know compared to Malay. The approach means "way of writing” (Student B).

“I don't think so. My confidence level might be fifty out of hundred. Sometimes if I use my own sentence, it doesn't sound as detailed and accurate as I want because I don't know how to express it correctly. But AI helps me to express it accurately” (Student D).

DISCUSSION

The mixed-method study provides valuable insights into the reliance level of L2 university students on AI tools in writing. This study highlights the significant role AI tools play in assisting students with their writing tasks, particularly in academic contexts. The most notable discovery of this research is that students exhibit a high reliance on AI tools when engaging in academic writing. This reliance is not merely a matter of convenience but is deeply integrated into their writing habits and processes. The study finds that AI tools, such as Quillbot, Grammarly, and ChatGPT, are used extensively to aid students in refining their language, improving coherence, and enhancing overall readability. While these tools offer substantial advantages in terms of efficiency and quality, they also introduce certain challenges. Students often find themselves dependent on these technologies, raising concerns about the potential impacts on their independent writing skills, originality, and critical thinking abilities.

In response to the reliance level of students on AI tools in writing, the quantitative data indicates that students sometimes use Quillbot, Grammarly, and ChatGPT for their writing tasks. This finding is reinforced by the qualitative data, wherein students explicitly mentioned that they use AI tools on a regular basis. Several key factors contribute to students' reliance on these tools, including the need to complete assignments within deadlines, the constraints of limited time, and the desire to achieve better grades. Many students reported that they rely on AI tools more heavily when facing a large number of assignments, as these tools assist in generating ideas, improving grammar, and ensuring coherence. Additionally, as deadlines approach, students tend to use AI tools more frequently to expedite the writing process. They also believe that AI tools enhance the quality of their work, ultimately helping them secure better grades. However, students remain cautious in their usage, acknowledging that the information generated by AI needs verification to ensure relevance and accuracy. They emphasized the importance of not copying content directly from AI-generated outputs, as the text could sometimes sound robotic or lack a natural academic flow. Lee et al. (2024) presented a differing perspective on the over-reliance on AI tools, arguing that excessive dependence on such technologies may hinder students' ability to develop essential writing skills. They suggested that reliance on AI tools could prevent students from independently understanding grammatical structures and identifying errors, thereby affecting their long-term writing proficiency.

The findings of this study further reinforce the assertion that students frequently use AI tools such as Quillbot, Grammarly, and ChatGPT. The usage patterns suggest a high level of dependence on these tools for academic purposes. Many students responded that they regularly utilize AI tools as they simplify their writing tasks and contribute to an overall smoother writing experience. One student mentioned that she often uses AI tools as they significantly ease her workload, allowing her to complete assignments more efficiently. Another student highlighted that he relies on AI tools consistently to enhance his writing quality, particularly when dealing with complex academic writing tasks. These responses demonstrate that AI tools have become an integral component of students' academic routines, offering substantial support in their writing endeavors.

Regarding the impact of AI tools on students' writing, the study's quantitative data reveals that participants generally agree on the benefits provided by AI tools. Many students believe that these tools help them write more efficiently, improve the fluency of their writing, make studying easier, enhance their writing skills, and serve as an effective means for completing assignments. The study further illustrates that when students face heavy workloads and tight deadlines, AI tools prove to be

indispensable in facilitating their writing process. The qualitative data corroborates these findings, as students provided positive feedback on their experiences using AI tools. Specifically, students noted that AI tools had significantly enriched their vocabulary, allowing them to express their ideas more effectively. Moreover, they reported that the formal tone of their writing had improved, making their work more polished and academically appropriate. Furthermore, AI tools assisted students in organizing their ideas cohesively, ensuring smoother transitions between paragraphs. These results align with the findings of Donnell et al. (2024), who reported similar benefits in terms of increased efficiency, time management, and improved assignment quality. However, contrasting viewpoints have been presented by Barrot (2023), who argued that ChatGPT, despite its advantages, has notable limitations as a language learning tool. He pointed out that AI-generated responses might sometimes be inaccurate, leading to misinformation and potential misunderstandings among students.

Additionally, the findings reveal that students maintain a positive attitude towards the integration of AI tools in their writing. Many students expressed that using AI tools enhances their confidence in writing, making them feel more assured about the quality of their work. This observation is consistent with the studies conducted by Al-Raimi et al. (2024), Hidayat and Sujarwati (2024), and Katsantonis and Katsantonis (2024), all of which emphasize the confidence-boosting effects of AI-assisted writing tools. However, not all responses were entirely optimistic. Some students raised concerns regarding the potential drawbacks of excessive AI reliance. A few participants admitted that they feared becoming overly dependent on AI tools, which could lead to diminished self-sufficiency in writing. They also expressed concerns about the ethical implications of AI-generated content, particularly the risk of plagiarism and academic dishonesty (Aisyi, 2024). Furthermore, Alqahtani (2024) highlighted an issue regarding students' varying levels of confidence in using AI writing tools. The study found that while some students were highly proficient in leveraging AI tools, others required additional training and guidance to maximize their benefits effectively. These findings suggest that while AI tools offer substantial advantages in academic writing, there is a need for balanced usage and proper education on ethical AI utilization to prevent over-dependence and ensure academic integrity.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of this research have important implications for educational practices. The study may help in looking at the suitable types of assignments that could help seeing students' actual potential rather than relying on AI tools to complete assignments. Pokkakillath and Suleri (2023) have similar thoughts that assessment requirements should be amended to avoid assessing biasedly when AI is involved. Although the excessive dependence on AI tools may raise concerns about the authenticity and originality of students work, it is essential to acknowledge the double-edged nature of this phenomenon. The research suggests that educational institutions should focus on evaluating students' higher-level skills, such as critical thinking, conceptual understanding, and problem-solving, rather than just detecting AI-generated content. This would be a more effective way to assess students' true potential, rather than relying on AI tools to complete assignments (Playfoot, Quigley, & Thomas, 2024; Fyfe, 2023).

The integration of AI in education should be carefully evaluated to ensure that it enhances students' learning experiences and academic growth, rather than diminishing them (Kamalov, Santandreu Calonge, & Gurrib, 2023). While the overreliance on AI tools may raise concerns about academic integrity and authenticity, it is essential to recognise the potential benefits of these technologies in supporting students learning and development. By adopting a balanced and thoughtful approach to AI integration, educational institutions can leverage the strengths of these tools while mitigating the risks and ensuring that students' academic growth and development remain the primary focus (Abbas, Ali, Manzoor, et al., 2023).

CONCLUSION

The study focuses on examining L2 students' reliance level in AI towards their idea's development and its effect. The research findings show that the students often use AI writing tools when it is involved with academic tasks. There are four main factors contributing to the students' reliance level: assignments completion, time constraint and achieving better grades. In addition, AI has significantly provided positive outcome towards students' ideas development and writing. The research suggests that AI-powered writing assistants can be beneficial for students, especially those who struggle with English proficiency or have difficulty expressing their ideas in writing.

Furthermore, the integration of AI-powered chatbots and conversational agents into the learning process can offer students interactive and engaging opportunities to practice their language skills, particularly in terms of reading fluency and spoken communication. However, it is important to approach the use of AI in English language education with a balanced perspective, carefully considering both the potential advantages and the potential limitations or risks associated with this technology.

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